

Conference Abstract

Investigating the role of LAX3 genes in abiotic stress response of the model legume *Medicago truncatula* and the crop plants soybean (*Glycine max*) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)

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Abstract

The growth of human population and adverse climate change such as water scarcity and high salinity, is a major challenge for agriculture and its efforts to meet the growing need for food worldwide. In most cultivated plants, salinization and drought cause nutrient deficiency, oxidative stress, biomass reduction and directly affect the quantity and quality of production (Kopecká et al. 2023). The share of research related to establishing the function of auxin transporter genes (*AUX/LAX*) under various abiotic stress factors in plants such as corn, soybean, potato, etc. has significantly increased (Jing et al. 2023).

The focus of the ongoing study was the model legume *Medicago truncatula* and the crop plants soybean (*Glycine max*) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*). Transgenic plants from *M. truncatula* and tomato, overexpressing the intracellular auxin transporter *MtLAX3* (Revalska et al. 2015), together with their wild types, were used as a platform for functional genomic and phenotypic analysis to reveal the role of *LAX3* genes in plant response to abiotic stresses salinity and drought (Fig. 1). Plants of two soybean cultivars, Richy and Izidor, serve as the foundation and starting point for transferring functional studies from model to cultivated species. Our working hypothesis assumes similar response of *LAX3* genes to drought and salinity stressors in all three plant species. The

overexpression of *MtLAX3* confers an advantage in plant development, which helps the transformants to overcome induced stress conditions more easily compared to the wild type. More in-depth studies related to the biochemical and metabolic profile of the plants are yet to be conducted in order to summarize and conclude the obtained results.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Comparative expression analysis of the *Medicago truncatula* auxin influx transporter gene *MtLAX3* (Medtr3g072870) and other *AUX/LAX* gene family members from the plant species soybean and tomato.

Keywords

LAX3, abiotic stress, *Medicago truncatula*, soybean, tomato, functional analysis

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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